

Effectiveness Of Teaching Critical Thinking On Psychological Capital And On Marital Intimacy Among Married Men And Women Of Tehran

Moosivand Mahboobeh*

Women Research Center, AL Zahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract:

Background: Critical thinking is a process that affects couples' intimacy. But the question is: does critical thinking affect the psychological capital and intimacy of married men and women? Aims: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of critical thinking training in increasing the psychological capital and intimacy of married men and women in Tehran. Method: The design of this study was quasi-experimental with a pretest-posttest with the control group. The statistical population of this study consisted of all couples who were referred to counseling centers in Tehran 2 in order to resolve their marital problems. The sample consisted of 90 couples referring to counseling centers who were selected by convenience sampling and were randomly assigned into two experimental and control groups. The research was conducted with the help of the Lutz et al. Questionnaire on psychological capital and parents' marital intimacy. Tools include McGee's Psychological Capital (2011), Parenting Marital Intimacy Questionnaire (2006), Critical Thinking Educational Protocol: Fisher's Critical Thinking Educational Content (2005), and Myers (1986). Data were analyzed using multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA). Results: Critical thinking training had an effect on the psychological capital and marital intimacy of couples ($p \geq 0/001$). Conclusions: Critical thinking training can increase psychological capital and marital intimacy of couples and therapists' families can use this educational method to improve the marital relationship of Iranian couples.

Keyword(s): Critical thinking, intimacy, psychological capital, couples